

Adaptive Performance and Teaching Competence of Out-of-Field English Teachers

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to establish the relationship of adaptive performance and teaching competence of the out-of-field English teachers teaching in schools operated by Teresian Daughters of Mary (TDM) in Davao City. To find answers to the aforementioned aims, the researcher employed the descriptive-correlational method of research. Using an adapted survey questionnaire, the researcher conducted a survey to the senior high school students of TDM-operated schools. The statistical tools used in interpreting the data were weighted mean, Pearson r and the multiple linear regression using the stepwise method. The findings of the study revealed that the overall mean score for adaptive performance of the out-of-field English teachers is good. Likewise, the overall mean score for the

teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers is good. Furthermore, it was found that there is a significant relationship between the adaptive performance and teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers teaching in TDM-operated schools. This finding, thus, allowed the researcher to reject the null hypothesis. Moreover, the multiple linear regression using the stepwise method revealed that the adaptive performance indicators including demonstrating interpersonal adaptability, demonstrating physically-oriented adaptability, handling emergencies on crisis, demonstrating cultural adaptability and handling work stress significantly influence the teaching competence of the teachers. Hence, these should be strengthened.

Keywords: *Adaptive Performance, Teaching Competence, Crisis Management, Instructional Practices*

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary educational landscape, effective classroom management serves as the bedrock of Teaching English, as described in the bounds of education, is noted as an act of concerted sharing of knowledge and experience which is organized within English as a discipline. It may also seek to imbue the avenue of being a profession that gives instruction, duly attributed by professionals called English teachers. In addition, these English teachers, per se, to be labeled as full-fledged educators teaching the discipline of English language, share the most set of criteria compelled in the profession, such as formal training, specialization in English, and the licensed professionals. These, among others, are considerations to maximize the optimum goals of teaching, especially training the young ones' intellect, skills, and attitude.

As time passes, the field of education and teaching has drastically evolved. With the new sets of curriculum, standards, and procedures, one may say that both the education and teaching endeavors are exceedingly at par from their traditional forms. However, even with these advancements, the scope of education and teaching still agonize from the phenomenon of out-of-field teaching.

In this regard, English teachers teaching out of their field of specialization have various sets of skills or behaviors that lead them to maintain performance during unexpected changes, otherwise known as adaptive performance, which directly induces impact on competence in the field down to offered quality education. Due to these unexpected changes, English teachers are expected to be more adaptable, flexible, and be better able to handle uncertainty than ever before (Pulakos, Arad, Donovan, & Plamondon, 2000).

In foreign countries, particularly in the United States of America, out-of-field teaching is intricately amassing a culture of incongruity as between 17 percent and 22 percent of US core classes are taught by teachers without a subject-related degree or certification (U.S. Education Department, 2010). The problem of out-of-field teaching, as identified, may be attributed to selective shortages of teachers including misplacement. According to Ingersoll (2003), each year, some of the out-of-field teaching practices take place in no more than half of all US secondary schools, whose students come from different low-income households. Apart from this notable problem, another exists upon the venue of out-of-field teachers.

Likewise, in Australia, out-of-field teaching remains a concern. In an article written by Weldon (2015), almost 20 percent of English teachers teach out of their field, 20 percent in Mathematics and Physics, 25 percent in History, 30 percent in Computing or IT, and 40 percent in Geography. With the data given, Australian schools yield good results at year twelve; on the other hand, out-of-field teaching within these schools is more likely to occur at the lower levels. Hence, imposing a threat to student achievement and teacher retention. While it is true that a high-quality teacher workforce is a necessary component of the provision of quality education, the Australian government required all teachers in Australia to be registered and obtain the necessary requisites in tertiary education, a four-year tertiary degree. Also, the said government uncapped funding the Initial Teacher Education courses to boost enrolment in the said program.

In the Philippines, particularly in Compostela Valley Province, out-of-field teaching is highly experienced. Since there were no qualified teachers who could teach certain subjects, the principal would consider competence as a criterion. However, within this given notion, teachers who teach out of their field of specialization feel unsatisfied of their performances and feel a number of detrimental effects of compromised credibility in line with their valued self-esteem; thus, affecting effective and competent teaching.

Out-of-field teaching, furthermore, is widespread in the Division of Davao City. A number of public and private schools resort to having their hired teachers teach other subjects not under their field of specialization as caused by compliance and teacher shortages. The adjustment for these teachers is never an easy task, as one needs to adapt to subject content and among others. Hence, affecting how they conduct classes and how they view teaching as a demanding profession.

Truly, the venue of out-of-field teaching, particularly noted on English teachers, signifies a thrust for concern, especially for English teachers who adapt to the notion of teaching other subjects along with their performance in the field. This issue, moreover, is delicate. As noted by Thomas and Brown (2011), teachers need to realize that to learn means to embrace what they do not know, come up with better questions about it, and continue asking questions in order to learn more. In other words, teachers, in this regard, are rooted to be adaptive while ensuring quality of teaching regardless of obstructions and or consequences experienced, as especially brought about by the out-of-field teaching phenomenon.

For this reason, this study is proposed to analyze the adaptive performance and teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers in TDM operated schools during the school year 2019-2020. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of adaptive performance of the out-of-field English teachers in TDM operated schools as perceived by students in terms of:
 - 1.1. solving problems creatively;
 - 1.2. learning work tasks, technologies, and procedures;
 - 1.3. demonstrating interpersonal adaptability;
 - 1.4. developing cultural adaptability;

- 1.5. demonstrating physically-oriented adaptability;
 - 1.6. handling emergencies or crisis situations;
 - 1.7. handling work stress; and,
 - 1.8. dealing with uncertain and unpredictable work?
2. What is the level of teaching competence of the out-of-field English teachers in TDM operated schools as perceived by students in terms of:
- 2.1. pre-instructional;
 - 2.2. instructional; and,
 - 2.3. post-instructional?
3. Is there any significant relationship between the level of adaptive performance and the level of teaching competence of English teachers in TDM operated schools?
4. Which of the indicators of adaptive performance significantly influence teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers?

Out-of-field teaching, as a phenomenon experienced by English teachers, directly suggests effects entirely affecting English teachers and students. Hobbs (2013) argued that there is an urgent need to understand the complexities surrounding out-of-field teaching. English teachers in the Philippines are well-faced with the out-of-field teaching phenomenon. When applying for a teaching position, English teachers are forced to teach out of their field to fit in the venue of shortages, since there is an unparalleled number of graduates among the disciplines under teacher-education programs in the Philippines, particularly in Davao City; hence, leading to stress. Kyriacou (2001) defined stress as the experience of negative or unpleasant emotions resulting from the various aspects of work. Hence, out-of-field English teachers' teaching performance when stressed is duly affected, such as subject preparation, classroom instruction, motivation to teach, among others.

However, Bayani and Guaho, Jr. (2016) noted that teachers teaching out of their fields, must possess distinct qualities that may help them become effective on teaching the subjects. They stressed that resourcefulness opens the door to greater accomplishments, a resourceful English teacher always finds a way for professional growth and development.

In the light of out-of-field teaching, a phenomenon that serves as one of the arrays of numerous challenges an English teacher is faced with, adaptability is necessary. Adaptability or Adaptive performance, per se, has been viewed in a number of aspects ranging from individual, team, and organizational levels (Pulakos, et al., 2000). According to Calarco (2016), adaptive performance has been frequently described as a set of skills or behaviors that lead a person to maintain performance during unexpected changes. In same manner, Johnson (2001) defined adaptive performance as the ability to adjust one's behavior with the requirements of the environment in a new situation.

As Thomas and Brown (2011) noted, teachers need to realize that to learn means to embrace what they do not know, come up with better questions about it, and continue asking questions to learn more. Hence, adaptability and adaptive performance yield an essential attribute an out-of-field English teacher must possess so as to spring forth better teaching quality.

The researcher, in this study, adapted the idea of Pulakos, et al. (2000), in line with the situated dimensions of adaptive performance linked with the venue of the out-of-field English teachers. These dimensions include solving problems creatively, learning work tasks, technologies and procedures, demonstrating interpersonal adaptability, demonstrating cultural adaptability, demonstrating a physically-oriented adaptability, handling emergencies or crisis situations, handling work stress, and dealing with uncertain and unpredictable work situations.

Within the scope of out-of-field teaching, as specifically experienced by English teachers, teaching still shall reflect quality. This is in view of the recently attributed Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers replacing and enhancing its old version as expressed through the National Competency Based

Teachers' Standards. The said framework believes that good teachers are vital to raising student-achievements. In other words, quality learning is contingent upon quality teaching (Department Order No. 42, 2017). Within Department Order No. 42, the researcher focused on domain one which encompasses the teachers' ability to apply developmentally appropriate and meaningful pedagogy grounded on content knowledge and current research. This, moreover, includes three paces, namely: Pre-instructional phase (Jacobsen et al, 1985), Instructional phase (Maheshwari, 2012), and Post-Instructional phase (Greenstein, 2010).

The quality of teachers remains equivocally the thrust of quality education, that is students learning and growing as individuals intellectually and skillfully equipped; that is if the out-of-field teaching is prevalent, adaptation is a necessity on the part of the teacher, particularly English teachers. By being adaptable, teachers are able to expand their knowledge and skills.

This study, furthermore, was anchored on the Theory of Psychological Constructivism by Dewey (1998) and the Reflective Practice Model by Schon (1987). According to Dewey (1998) the Theory of Psychological Constructivism stresses that a person learns by mentally organizing and reorganizing new information or experiences. Moreover, the organization happens partly by relating new experiences to prior knowledge that is already meaningful and well understood. In this study, as its central focus, English teachers in TDM operated schools under the umbrella of the Archdiocese of Davao who teach other subjects they do not specialize at have various perspectives upon dealing with the issue of out-of-field teaching, per se. With this in view, English teachers organize and re-organize the knowledge they received from their undergraduate studies and the contexts and/or information they gathered from the actual teaching endeavor by means of adaptation and later on affecting their efficiency in the teaching field. This says that English teachers construct knowledge while relating knowledge at hand with situated new experiences, in same way as adjustments made, such as strategies and the likes, while teaching other subjects.

Additionally, the Reflective Model as inspired by Schon (1987) significantly attributes connection within the study at hand. According to Schon (1987), this model primarily emphasizes the reconstruction of professional knowledge not as theoretical or discipline based but as derived and constructed from the everyday judgments and experience of practitioners. With the reflective practice model in view, this study relates the adaptive performance of the aforementioned teachers as flexible and differing; henceforth, affecting teaching quality and competence. Also, within the context of the model, this study particularly paves way to re-viewing the profession taken and reconstructing knowledge and perception of and from the profession based on personal judgments and everyday experiences and encounters.

METHODS

Research Design

Since the main purpose of this research is to investigate whether there is any correlation between the adaptive performance and teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers in TDM operated schools, this research imbued the descriptive-correlational method through conducting survey. According to McMillan (2012), educational researchers use this approach when the purpose of their study is to describe the relationships between variables within a given population.

The descriptive-correlational method is used in this research since it is intended to investigate the correlation of two variables (Arikunto, 2007), namely, adaptive performance and teaching competence of English teachers in TDM schools who teach other subjects they do not specialize at. Moreover, correlation coefficient is used to appropriately classify the degree of correlation between the two variables, per se. This notion is supported by Creswell (2012) as he notes down that researchers use the correlation statistical test to describe and measure the degree of relationship or association between two or more variables or set of scores. This also implied that the researcher in this research did not attempt to manipulate the variables at hand; instead, the researcher will ultimately relate the variables using the aforementioned method.

In line with this, this study employed a specific type of correlational method, the explanatory design; since this study will investigate and analyze the degree of relationship or association between two variables. The explanatory design, as noted by Creswell (2012), allows the researcher to view relationships of two variables at hand, that is where changes in one variable are reflected in changes in the other.

Research Locale

The study was conducted within institutions in the Archdiocese of Davao operated by TDM nuns under the mandate of the Davao City Archbishop. These institutions were observed to practice the out-of-field teaching endeavor, as specifically experienced by their hired English teachers, this academic year 2019 – 2020.

The respondents of this study were the High School students of TDM operated schools under the umbrella of the Archdiocese of Davao. Specifically, one class per TDM operated school under the instruction of an out-of-field English teacher will be purposively selected. These students, per se, conceive various perspectives pertaining to the adaptive performance and teaching competence of their out-of-field English teachers, especially as they teach subjects they do not specialize at.

Sampling Technique

In selecting the respondents of the study, the researcher utilized the avenue of purposive sampling. This sampling technique, according to Arikunto (2010), is the process of selecting sample by taking subject that is not based on the level or area, but it is taken based on a specific purpose. Riyanto (2001) also stated that purposive sampling is oriented on choosing the sample population with a purpose that is specific to the researched matter. He also added that purposive sampling is used by the researchers to choose a sample population who were representatives of a given population. Suffice to say, purposive sampling is a process by which the researcher uses the judgment of an expert in selecting cases or it selects cases with a specific purpose in mind. Purposive sampling is used most often when a difficult-to-reach population needs to be measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Adaptive Performance of the Out-of-field English Teachers in TDM Operated Schools

Table 1. *Level of Adaptive Performance of the Out-of-field English Teachers in TDM Operated Schools*

Adaptive Performance	Mean	SD	Description
Handling Emergencies on crisis	3.15	0.74	Good
Handling work stress	3.03	0.52	Good
Dealing with uncertain and unpredictable work situations	3.13	0.54	Good
Solving problems creatively	3.10	0.57	Good
Learning work tasks, technologies, and procedures	3.10	0.53	Good
Demonstrating interpersonal adaptability	3.12	0.56	Good
Demonstrating cultural adaptability	2.40	0.70	Fair

Demonstrating physically-oriented adaptability	2.81	0.47	Good
Overall	2.98	0.40	Good

Specifically, among the eight indicators situated under the adaptive performance scale for out-of-field English teachers, the indicator handling emergencies on crisis received the highest mean score of 3.15 which can be translated or interpreted as good. Moreover, the data implies that the out-of-field English teachers when faced with crisis situations during class sessions, such as student-related accidents, fortuitous events, and the likes, are able to maintain focus and objectivity allowing them to still carry out their tasks as teachers in various subject areas whilst performing their roles as facilitators of learning.

In the study conducted by Brown (2008), she noted that based on the findings of her study, school teachers must be assessed with their safety needs and must be given ample training activities to help them feel adequately trained pertaining to handling emergencies on crisis situations. Huitt (2004) also stated that according to Maslow’s theory, deficiencies in fulfillment of other needs will occur if the physiological and safety needs of an individual are not met first. Thus, out-of-field English teachers perform at optimum levels when their safety and other needs are fulfilled.

Dealing with uncertain and unpredictable work situations as the second highest indicator under adaptive performance with a mean score of 3.13 which means good. This implies that the out-of-field English teachers readily respond to uncertainties inside the classroom during class sessions so as to perform efficiently the task at hand; thus, allowing them to act appropriately during unexpected happenings even without sufficient details leading towards still performing their assigned teaching endeavor. Teaching is evidently and inevitably uncertain (Floden & Clark, 1988). No teacher can be sure of how a lesson will go. No one can be sure of what teaching approach will be most successful within a group of students. Hence, adaptability, as manifested through dealing with uncertain and unpredictable work situations, is highly relevant to teachers given that teaching work involves responding to and managing constant change (Collie & Martin, 2015).

The third highest indicator situates demonstrating interpersonal adaptability with the mean score of 3.12 referred to as good. The data suggests that the out-of-field English teachers efficiently show an adaptive behavior towards dealing with students inside the classroom during class sessions. This is in line with the findings stressed within the study conducted by Pennings et al (2017). It stated the expectation that teachers are the ones who shall be able to refrain from hostility and subordinate behavior inside classrooms. Furthermore, they found out that a substantial number of teachers are able to refrain from responding with hostility as well as refrain from reacting subordinately to dominant student bids; marking the relationship of the teachers towards the students as interpersonally adaptive, leading through a healthy communication and relationship inside the classroom.

The indicators solving problems creatively and learning work tasks, technologies and procedure are noted as the fourth highest indicators having the mean score of 3.10 which is interpreted as good. . In terms of the indicator, solving problems creatively, the data revealed that the out-of-field English teachers are perceived to resourcefully solve difficulties and setbacks inside the classroom during class sessions. It indicates that the out-of-field English teachers provide appropriate ideas and strategies to solve problems experienced. This means that the out-of-field English teachers are perceived to be progressive and liberal when faced with challenges inside the classroom.

Solving problems creatively inside the classroom for an out-of-field English teacher is not an overall easy task. Gonzalez (2016) identified common classroom problems experienced by teachers when conducting classes and the creative solutions these teachers may apply. One of which includes brainstorming for ideas during writing classes. As students are found to be slow in coming up for ideas,

teachers or out-of-field English teachers may use inspiration boards as suggested. Furthermore, a common classroom problem may also involve the students' low understanding of complex topics due to vocabulary.

Similarly, in terms of learning work tasks, technologies and procedure, the data showed that the out-of-field English teachers are well-attributed to the use of technology inside the classroom during class sessions. Hussain (2008) stressed in his study that one of the functions of education is the preparation of students for life. In these modern times, teachers are no longer the sole source of information inside the classroom; instead, more student-centered approaches are encouraged to maximize optimum learning and experience.

The fifth highest indicator is handling work stress with a mean score of 3.03 or *good*. This implies that the out-of-field English teachers, when faced with a number of stressors inside the classroom during class sessions, are notably calm and deal with the faced difficulty with sound mind that do not rattle easily nor act angrily. Teaching has consistently been found to be one of the most stressful professions, and studies show that teachers across the globe are exposed to constant stressors brought about by a number of sources (Hartney, 2008; Kyriacou, 2001) including teaching subjects they do not specialize at. Yet, with effective stress management, teachers, including out-of-field English teachers, may overcome the brought about effects of stress. The teachers' ability to manage professional stress impacts their teaching effectiveness (Steinhardt, et al, 2011).

Demonstrating physically-oriented adaptability, as the sixth highest indicator, has the mean score of 2.81 or *good*. This implies that the out-of-field English teachers while conducting classes are observed to make sure that the classroom is well-arranged and appropriately intact. According to Hannah (2013), one of the first areas that make a noticeable impact on student success is the physical environment of the classroom. When students first step inside the classroom, they will make a judgment about the type of class they will be taking. And, as noted by Dixon (2007), appropriate attire has determined the art of social and cultural styles and whether individuals are deemed trustworthy or believable may be influenced by their appearance.

The lowest indicator is demonstrating cultural adaptability which gained a mean score of 2.40 or *fair*. This implies that the out-of-field English teachers are unexceptionally sensitive to the varying needs of the respondents that may include respecting customs and beliefs, understanding family orientations and among others. According to Vaccarino (2009), teachers are aware of cultural differences among students inside the classroom and do not want to have a negative effect on their students' learning by possibly being culturally insensitive, or placing undue stress on them by upsetting their existing educational and cultural beliefs. As noted, fair for out-of-field English teachers, adapting to students' varied cultures is a necessity to seemingly accentuate learning inside the classroom.

Level of Teaching Competence of the Out-of-field English Teachers in TDM Operated Schools

Table 2. *Level of Teaching Competence of the Out-of-field English Teachers in TDM Operated Schools*

Areas of Competence	Mean	SD	Description
Pre-Instructional	3.22	0.56	Good
Instructional	3.20	0.54	Good
Post-Instructional	3.24	0.56	Good
Overall	3.22	0.50	Good

Among the three indicators under teaching competence, the post-instructional indicator is perceived by the respondents as highest having a mean score of 3.24. The aforesaid indicator is interpreted as *good*. It indicates that the English teachers teaching other subjects effectually conducts post-instructional activities designed to provide enrichment and generalization of learning at the end of the learners. This is in line with the idea set foot by Greenstein (2010) which stated that teachers, whether teaching in their field of specialization or teaching other subjects, are regularly asked to account for their students' learning. This accounting occurs throughout the instructional process, from lesson planning and pre-assessment to post-instructional assessments; hence, assessing for and enriching learning through generalizations and/or assignments is particularly relevant at the end of instruction.

The second highest indicator is the pre-instructional part of the session which is regarded by the respondents as good having the mean score of 3.22. It, further, indicates that the out-of-field English teachers, regardless of the topic or subject they have to teach, conduct appropriate class customary endeavors which may include 'prayer, attendance and the likes. According to Jacobsen et al. (1985), pre-instruction as utilized by teachers around the globe, including those of which who teach other subjects apart from their specialization, is necessary and points out that planning is the key to an effective teaching.

The instructional part of the session, which is perceived by the respondents as good having the mean score of 3.20, is considered the lowest indicator under teaching competence. This implies that the English teachers teaching other subjects effectually attribute the conduct of the following, to wit: introduce topic in an interesting and engaging way, review of topics discussed, use of varied activities and learning resources, provide opportunities for collaboration, asks thought-provoking questions, solicit learning difficulties and address them, and organize class time. Maheshwari (2012) noted that the phase of teaching under the interactive or instructional part of the lesson provides learning experiences to students in suitable modes. Therefore, content of the topic at hand is attributed with various classroom, laboratory, or natural familiarities with pre-determined goals and objectives designed for the time being.

As presented in Table 2, the level of teaching competence of the out-of-field English teachers gets an overall mean score of 3.22 or good. This means that the out-of-field English teachers appropriately conduct the various activities situated under pre-instructional, instructional, and post-instructional parts of the session. Furthermore, this implies that even the English teachers teach other subjects they do not specialize at, they are still noted to perform the teaching task following within the given indicators practically and properly, though not excellently. Teaching, as a profession, is recognized as demanding and stressful (Griffith, Steptoe, & Copley, 1999). Research has revealed that teachers are exposed to various sources of stress involving a demanding workload (Kyriacou, 2001) brought about by factors including teaching subjects they do not specialize at; hence, affecting their competence in the job and eventually placing in grave danger the venue of effectiveness in the field. However, according to Nessipbayeva (2012), teachers need a wide range of competencies in order to face the complex challenges of today's world. Taking into account that teachers are central figures in the educational process, the success in education depends on the teachers' preparation, erudition, and performance quality.

The third target of this study is to deliberately determine the relationship between the Level of Adaptive Performance and the Level of Teaching Competence of English teachers teaching other subjects. Table 3 provides the necessary information intended to answer this target.

Test of Relationship between the Level of Adaptive Performance and the Level of Teaching Competence of English Teachers in TDM Operated Schools

Table 3. *Test of Relationship between the Level of Adaptive Performance and the Level of Teaching Competence of English Teachers in TDM Operated Schools*

Variables	Pearson Correlation (r)	Coefficient of Determination (R ²)	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision ($\alpha = 0.05$)
Level of Adaptive Performance and Level of Teaching Performance	0.78	0.61	High	0.000	Significant (Reject H ₀)

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test if there is a significant relationship between the level of adaptive performance and the level of teaching competence of English teachers in TDM operated schools at a 0.05 level of significance. The results show that there is a significant high relationship (R, 0.78; p, <0.05) between the level of adaptive performance and the level of teaching competence of English teachers in TDM operated schools at a 0.05 level of significance.

In addition, the results show that 61 percent (R², 0.61) of the variances or variation of the level of teaching competence of English teachers can be accounted for or associated by their level of adaptive performance. Lastly, the results further imply that improving the teachers' level of adaptive performance would result to the improvement of their level of teaching competence.

Collie and Martin (2015) contend that the concept of adaptability is highly relevant to teachers given that teaching work involves responding to and managing constant change; for example, if a teacher is asked to teach a subject that is unfamiliar to him or her, effectively dealing with this change requires regulating thoughts to find connections between the new material and familiar topics, regulating behavior to seek out a helpful person who has more knowledge and relevant resources in the new subject, and regulating emotions such as anxiety or excitement, to focus on finding a solution in a focused and timely manner.

Researchers also considered the role of adaptability not only in instruction but also in teachers' functioning at work (Hargreaves, 2005; Mansfield et al., 2012). For instance, Mansfield et al. (2012) examined descriptions from early career teachers of what it means to be a resilient teacher and demonstrated that being adaptable and flexible were appropriate requirements. Furthermore, in the study conducted by the aforementioned author(s), respondents noted that adaptability involves actions such as adjusting to new roles, accepting changes, and having a 'plan b'. Hence, adaptability or being adaptive to situations is a necessary term aiding an employee, particularly an out-of-field English teacher, to increase his or her performance or competence at work that is notably immersed to change.

Indicators of Adaptive Performance that Significantly Influence Teaching Competence of Out-of-field English Teachers

Table 4. *Indicators of Adaptive Performance that Significantly Influence Teaching Competence of Out-of-field English Teachers*

Indicators of Adaptive Performance (AP)					p-value	Decision at a 0.05 Level
	B	SE	Beta	t-stat		
(Constant)	0.43	0.17		2.51	0.01	

Demonstrating Interpersonal Adaptability (DIA)	0.31	0.06	0.33	5.08	0.00	Significant
Demonstrating Physically-Oriented Adaptability (DPOA)	0.24	0.07	0.25	3.72	0.00	Significant
Handling Emergencies on Crisis (HEC)	0.17	0.05	0.18	3.15	0.00	Significant
Demonstrating Cultural Adaptability (DCA)	0.13	0.06	0.15	2.05	0.04	Significant
Handling Work Stress (HWS)	0.07	0.03	0.09	2.02	0.05	Significant

Regression Model:

$$TC = 0.43 + 0.31 (DIA) + 0.24 (DPOA) + 0.17 (HEC) + 0.13 (DCA) + 0.07 (HWS)$$

Durbin Watson: 1.56; F: 61.751; p-value: 0.00

Excluded Variable	Beta	t	p-value	Decision at a 0.05 Level
Solving problems creatively	0.07	1.35	0.18	Not Significant
Learning work tasks, technologies, and procedures	0.02	0.31	0.76	Not Significant
Dealing with uncertain and unpredictable work situations	0.06	0.91	0.37	Not Significant

The Multiple Linear Regression Model using the Stepwise Method was used to determine the indicators of adaptive performance that significantly influence teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers at a 0.05 level of significance.

The results show that the indicators, Demonstrating Interpersonal Adaptability (DIA) (B, 0.31; p, <0.05), Demonstrating Physically-Oriented Adaptability (DPOA) (B, 0.24; p, <0.05), Handling Emergencies on Crisis (HEC) (B, 0.17; p, <0.05), Demonstrating Cultural Adaptability (DCA) (B, 0.13; p, <0.05), and Handling Work Stress (HWS) (B, 0.07; p, <0.05) significantly influence teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers at a 0.05 level of significance.

Furthermore, the generated Regression Model, $TC = 0.43 + 0.31 (DIA) + 0.24 (DPOA) + 0.17 (HEC) + 0.13 (DCA) + 0.07 (HWS)$ shows that for every unit increase in the indicators Demonstrating Interpersonal Adaptability (DIA), Demonstrating Physically-Oriented Adaptability (DPOA), Handling Emergencies on Crisis (HEC), Demonstrating Cultural Adaptability (DCA), and Handling Work Stress (HWS), the level of teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers would significantly increase by 0.31, 0.24, 0.17, 0.13, and 0.07 units respectively at a 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the out-of-field English teachers deal with others especially students in a flexible and open-minded manner, adjust to the physical embodiments within the bounds of the classroom, react to urgencies leading towards making split-second decisions, value climate-orientation needs integrating well-adjusted efforts towards understanding and adjusting to various customs and opinions of students, and manage frustrations brought about by the difficult circumstances in order to dynamically improve their competence as expressed through the various phases of instruction. As the out-of-field English teachers depart from the concepts of viewing learning as a prerequisite to performance (Pulakos, Arad, Donovan, & Plamondon, 2000), they develop the concept of learning being part of the performance itself (London & Smither, 1999), vis-à-vis; thus, incorporating the venues of adaptation and adjustment necessary to increase their competence in teaching, especially as they teach subjects they do not specialize at.

On the other hand, the indicators, Solving Problems Creatively (SPC) (B, 0.07; $p, >0.05$), Learning Work Tasks, Technologies, and Procedures (LWTTP) (B, 0.02; $p, >0.05$), and Dealing with Uncertain and Unpredictable Work Situations (DUUWS) (B, 0.06; $p, >0.05$) do not significantly influence teaching competence of out-of-field English teachers at a 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the out-of-field English teachers improve their teaching competence without having to necessarily tap the avenues of being innovative reflected within the use of varied and available resources, learning new approaches and keeping knowledge and skills current as manifested through research, and taking effective course of actions despite unpredictability of situations at hand. However, the importance of the aforementioned variables, namely: Solving Problems Creatively, Learning Work Tasks, Technologies, and Procedures, and Dealing with Uncertain and Unpredictable Work Situations is undeniable in the bounds of teaching. As stated by Pulakos (2000), to improve adaptive performance is to hone these necessary variables or indicators; hence, improving, as well, teaching competence.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are presented:

The adaptive performance of the out-of-field English teachers, along with its indicators, is relatively performed as appropriately effective. Out-of-field English teachers endeavor to be adaptive in relation to their experienced displacement of relating to teaching subject or subjects they do not specialize at.

The teaching competence of the out-of-field English teachers, along with its indicators, is relatively performed as appropriately effective. Out-of-field English teachers effectively perform their instructional assignment upon teaching the subject or subjects they do not specialize at, reflecting an efficient performance within the three main indicators of teaching competence directly hailed as pre-instructional, instructional, and post-instructional phases of the lesson.

Since statistically there is a significant relationship between two or more variables, there is a probability that the teaching competence of the out-of-field English teachers is caused to increase or decline by their level of adaptive performance in line with teaching subject or subjects they do not specialize at.

To further improve the teaching competence of the out-of-field English teachers, the out-of-field English teachers may set focus on putting up more effort on developing their adaptive performance in Demonstrating Interpersonal Adaptability, Demonstrating Physically-Oriented Adaptability, Handling Emergencies on Crisis, Demonstrating Cultural Adaptability and Handling Work Stress. The aforementioned teachers may seek to take a full advantage of these indicators under adaptive performance to increase more their level of teaching competence as they teach other subjects they do not specialize at; also, to aid students' comprehension of the subject or subjects they intend to teach.

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